

Some Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with 2,5-Dihydroxyacetophenone Schiff Bases

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The composition of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-2,5-dichloroaniline (DHAPADA) and *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-*p*-toluidine (DHAPAT) has been found to be 1 : 2 (M : L). Structural assessment of the complexes has been made on the basis of the results of magnetic moments, and electronic and ir spectral studies.

COMPLEXES of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with ligands containing nitrogen and oxygen as donor atoms have been described in the literature¹⁻⁴. The present communication reports the results of spectrophotometric studies of the complex formation of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with DHAPADA and DHAPAT.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade (B.D.H. or E. Merck). The Schiff bases, *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-2,5-dichloroaniline and *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-*p*-toluidine were prepared⁵ by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone and 2,5-dichloroaniline/*p*-toluidine in ethanol for 4.5 h. The contents were cooled, filtered and the products washed with solvent ether (b.p. 60-80°). The products were crystallised from ethanol to give the compounds (decomp. points 94.5° and 122°).

Composition of complexes: Equimolar solutions of the metal chlorides (CoCl_2 or NiCl_2) and ligand (DHAPADA or DHAPAT) were mixed in the ratio 1 : 3, 1 : 2, 1 : 1 and 2 : 1, and the final volume was made upto 20 ml by adding the required amount of ethanol. The maximum absorption of the solutions was found to be 370 nm (with Co^{II}) and 520 nm (with Ni^{II}) in all the cases, indicating thereby, the formation of only one type of complex with the ligand.

The stoichiometry (M : L) of the complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation, molar ratio and slope ratio methods. The methods suggested 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the complexes which was further confirmed by conductometry and elemental analyses.

Isolation of the complexes: A mixture of metal chloride (CoCl_2 or NiCl_2) (20.0 ml, 0.02 *M*) and

the ligand (40.0 ml, 0.02 *M*) in ratio 1 : 2 was refluxed in ethanol for 1 h. On cooling, brown or brown red crystals were deposited which were filtered, washed with water and dried *in vacuo*.

The metal chelates were found to be soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance value in DMF medium (10^{-3} *M*) $40 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, indicate a non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined cryoscopically using benzene as solvent and confirms the proposed composition of the complexes.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. Electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer model 521 spectrophotometer. The colour and elemental analyses are listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt complexes: The observed magnetic moments for Co^{II} complexes (4.49 and 4.60 B.M.) are slightly less than the usual values for the high-spin octahedral cobalt complexes. This may be due to the incomplete quenching⁶ of the orbitals of the metal ion during chelation leading to low-spin octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes (3) and (4) consist of two main bands appearing at 9000, 9550 and 23500, 24000 cm^{-1} , respectively. The highest and lowest energy bands are assigned to γ_8 and γ_1 transitions, whereas the two shoulders ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ (18650 and 18540 cm^{-1} , respectively) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (20850 and 20600 cm^{-1} , respectively) either may be due to the splitting of γ_8 in many components or may be due to γ_8 transition⁷. The ratio γ_8/γ_1 for Co^{II} complexes in

octahedral fields was found⁹⁻¹⁰ to lie in the range 1.80-2.20. However, for the present Co^{II} complexes (3) and (4), this ratio appear to be 2.07 and 1.94, respectively indicating thereby 20850 and 20600 cm⁻¹ are due to γ_2 transition. The values of nephelauxetic ratio arising out of partial overlap of 3d orbitals with the σ and π orbitals of surrounding donors consist of both $f^2\sigma$ and $f^2\pi$, i.e. $f^2 = f^2\pi \cdot f^2\sigma$ and are 1.13 and 1.19 for the complexes (3) and (4), respectively. Thus, the spectral data indicate a octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} complexes.

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSES DATA

Sl. no.	Compound	Colour	Analyses % ; Found/(Calcd.)*		
			N	OI	Metal
1.	DHAPADA	Brown	4.60 (4.70)	23.72 (23.90)	—
2.	DHAPAT	Brown	5.72 (5.80)	—	—
3.	[(DHAPADA) ₂ Co(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	4.12 (4.08)	20.90 (20.73)	8.52 (8.62)
4.	[(DHAPAT) ₂ Co(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown red	4.90 (4.87)	—	10.20 (10.24)
5.	[(DHAPADA) ₂ Ni(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	4.17 (4.09)	20.90 (20.74)	8.67 (8.57)
6.	[(DHAPAT) ₂ Ni(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown red	4.80 (4.87)	—	10.26 (10.26)

*Satisfactory C and H analyses found.

Nickel complexes : The magnetic moment value (3.00 B.M.) observed for the Ni^{II} complex (6) is comparable with the assignment of octahedral configuration¹¹. If in case of Ni^{II}, symmetry is allowed to be lower than cubic and if low-symmetry component is larger, then spin-paired term may be found in the neighbored¹². At low temperatures it reaches diamagnetism whilst as the temperature increases, the magnetic moment approaches the spin-free value. X-Ray investigation^{13,14} of paramagnetic (2.54 B.M.) bis-(mesostilbenediamine)nickel(II) dichloroacetate, has shown that crystal of this complex consists of a mixture of paramagnetic octahedral molecules and diamagnetic planar molecules. The subnormal magnetic moment (2.60 B.M.) observed for the complex (5) may be assumed to be intermediate between that of the low-spin state and high-spin state. It appears that the energy difference between the singlet and triplet is comparable with the thermal energy (kT). This has been possible due to the lowering of symmetry¹⁵ from O_h→D_{4h}. In octahedral complexes, the singlet state lies above triplet states. As the field along the Z-axis decreases, the triplet state comes closer to the singlet state, thus allowing partial thermal transition resulting in the decrease of magnetic moment.

Four bands have been observed in the electronic spectra of the complex (5) at 8000, 13000 (sh), 15200 and 26500 cm⁻¹. The latter two bands are characteristic of an octahedral complex¹⁶, whereas the former two bands may be a consequence of γ_1 split-

ing due to low symmetry of the ligand field or due to the spin-forbidden transitions¹⁷. In the electronic spectra of complex (6), three spin-allowed bands at 9900, 16500 and 27500 cm⁻¹ have been observed. The value of interelectronic repulsion parameter (β) comes out to be 953 cm⁻¹ as against free-ion value¹⁸ (1080 cm⁻¹). These observations suggest on octahedral symmetry for Ni^{II} complexes.

Ir spectral studies : The assignment of the important ir bands in the complexes has been compared with the spectrum of the free ligands. The ir spectrum of the ligands (DHAPADA and DHAPAT) show bands around 1600-1640 cm⁻¹ (azomethine) and 3280-3300 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH). The metal complexes register lower values for azomethine (~1600 and 1560 cm⁻¹) indicating coordination of the ligand through azomethine nitrogen. The phenolic-OH stretching frequencies are also shifted to region 3250-3275 cm⁻¹ on complexation with Co^{II} and Ni^{II}. This view is further supported by the appearance of bands corresponding to ν_{M-N} (530 cm⁻¹) and ν_{M-O} (450 cm⁻¹). The presence of coordinated water in all the complexes is indicated by bands around 3400 (sh), 865 (w) and 700 cm⁻¹ (w), assignable to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations, respectively.

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